

Oxytocin receptor is a major biologic determinant of completed suicide in humans.

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We used RNA-sequencing in the human brain, controlling for major depression diagnosis for discovery of genes important for suicide completion in humans. We report here discovery of the oxytocin receptor and its transcriptional activation in the brain as a basic requirement for suicide completion in humans.

Citations

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